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Milestone 13: Cultural Heritage Test Ingest

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CODATA-ICSTI	Committee on Data of the International Science Council - International Council for Scientific and Technical Information
DRI	Digital Repository of Ireland
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums
IIIF	International Image Interoperability Framework
LOD	Linked Open Data
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance

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1. Introduction

The purpose of WorldFAIR WP13 (Cultural Heritage) is to promote alignment between practices in the cultural heritage sector and implementations of the FAIR principles in other research domains¹. Recognising that there is already a great diversity in policy and standards underpinning the professional delivery of cultural heritage data in both public and private institutions in this sector, specifically Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums (or ‘GLAM’ organisations), WP13 proposed to narrow the scope of the case study to practices supporting the sharing of digital image formats (e.g. TIFF, JPEG, PNG, etc.), which already provide a connection point within and across the cultural heritage sector. If agreement can be reached on changing image sharing to better support the FAIR principles, then other types of data may more easily be made interoperable with data in other domains of practice as well.

This WorldFAIR Milestone report describes the development of a case study for FAIR-aligned image sharing in the cultural heritage domain, and details the technical implementation carried out in the test environment at the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI), Ireland’s national repository for cultural heritage, humanities and social sciences data.

This Milestone contributes to an understanding of the D13.3 ‘DRI Case Study Report’² which outlines in greater detail the context, discussion, actions and results of DRI’s response to the five broadly generalisable recommendations produced by a coordinated working group of cultural heritage professionals for D13.2 ‘Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report’³. Both of these deliverables followed on the publication of D13.1 ‘Cultural Heritage Mapping Report: Practices and policies supporting cultural heritage image sharing platforms’, which demonstrated the ways in which image data and metadata interoperability had already been explored within the cultural heritage sector⁴.

¹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

² Murphy, J., Knazook, B., O’Carroll, A., Cassidy, K., Long, K., Kenny, S. (2024). WorldFAIR Project (D13.3) Implementation and Testing of Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations: DRI Case Study Report (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10850009>

³ Knazook, B., Murphy, J., Barner, K., Cassidy, K., Claeysens, S., Cortese, C., Manchester, E. J., Padilla, T., Reijerkerk, D., Robson, G., Schmidt, A., Sherratt, T., & Warren, M. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D13.2) Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7897244>

⁴ Knazook, B., & Murphy, J. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D13.1) Cultural Heritage Mapping Report: Practices and policies supporting Cultural Heritage image sharing platforms (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7659002>

2. Scope and limitations

Given the WorldFAIR project timelines, and the availability of DRI staff time being offered in-kind, it was understood that fully approved and adopted responses to all of D13.2's recommendations may not be realised within the project timeframe. Instead, the project was developed to target results in at least two recommendations and to kick-start discussions on the remaining recommendations to establish a publicly available plan.

This report represents a particular moment in time – it marks the end of a period of intense work to develop FAIR-aligned recommendations for the cultural heritage sector, but also the beginning of a period of change for DRI as it begins to engage with the recommendations and advocate for the Collections as Data movement through institutional support for the newly formed [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\) Collections as Data Interest Group](#)⁵ and the biennial [Digital Preservation for the Arts, Social Sciences and Humanities \(DPASSH\) Conference](#),⁶ this year focused on the theme of 'Collections as Data / Data as Collections.' The extent of organisational and cultural change spurred by these activities should not be underestimated.

2.1. Culture change vs. technical change

When the WorldFAIR WP13 case study was first proposed, it was anticipated that the results delivered at the end of the project would be primarily technical in nature. As seen above, this Milestone was anticipated to record a 'Test Ingest' of cultural heritage material into the repository, which suggests that existing ingest processes would need to be modified to accommodate either new fields or new functionality.

While there are several functional changes being tested in response to two of the recommendations, these necessitated – and are underpinned by – considerable discussion around DRI's role in communicating versus mandating member practices. DRI is a CoreTrustSeal-certified preservation infrastructure designed to support member organisations in aligning themselves with recommended best practice in managing and preserving cultural heritage, humanities and social science data. In most cases, the changes being implemented are those which present options for depositors or end users to select in addition to the options already available in the repository. In the case of the changes made to rights fields in particular, the new functionality will only be applied to

⁵ Research Data Alliance (20 Feb 2024). Collections as Data IG Charter (transitioning from Archives and Records Professionals for Research Data IG). Research Data Alliance.

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/archives-and-records-professionals-research-data-ig/case-statement/collections-dat-a-ig-charter>

⁶ Digital Preservation for the Arts, Social Sciences and Humanities (2024). DPASSH. <https://dpassh.org/>

new deposits as it will take some time to ensure adoption across legacy collections deposited prior to the work of this project.

It is further recognised that training to ensure a consistent approach to digital objects and their metadata form a key component of any effort to change how cultural heritage is viewed within the research paradigm. This will be a continuing endeavour for DRI long after the conclusion of the current WorldFAIR project.

3. Summary of recommendations and key actions

In D13.3, these recommendations are addressed in some detail.

	Description	Actions
Recommendation 1 Citation Model	A formal citation model for cultural heritage images should be adopted which recognises digital surrogates as research objects and includes references to revisions of either image data or metadata	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Review current citation model <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Propose changes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Test choices against metadata in the repository <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Modify as needed <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Revise DRI Citation Policy ⁷
Recommendation 2 Transparency	Information about the creation, management and preservation of files should be visible and understandable by both humans and machines	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Survey membership about digitisation practices <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Analyse survey results and review image files in the repository <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Report on findings <input type="checkbox"/> Develop guidelines for utilising embedded metadata and documenting file creation and management practices
Recommendation 3 Data Documentation	The process of selection, scope and completeness of the data should	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Review the advice available for adding contextual metadata to

⁷ Digital Repository of Ireland. (2024, January 8). DRI Citation Policy 2022. Digital Repository of Ireland.. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.7d27pn025>

	always be documented	<p>collections</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Trial the Datasheet for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets⁸ <input type="checkbox"/> Develop additional guidance if needed
<p>Recommendation 4</p> <p>Licensing and Rights</p>	Description	Actions
	Rights, licences and labels should be applied consistently and in a standardised way	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Review DRI's documentation on rights and licences for both metadata and data⁹ <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Promote visibility of the CC0 licence for metadata, and clearly indicate any exceptions <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Add standardised Rights Statements to rights field options¹⁰ <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Remove non-standard licences from the licence field options <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Update guidance
<p>Recommendation 5</p> <p>Delivery</p>	Description	Actions
	Improved support for identifier schemes, APIs and machine-readable contextual data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Identification of potential actions that could improve technical delivery of images <input type="checkbox"/> Creation of use cases to inform technical development

Table 1 - Summary of Recommendations from D13.2 and agreed actions from D13.3

⁸ Alkemade, H., Claeysens, S., Colavizza, G., Freire, N., Irollo, A., Lehmann, J., Neudecker, C., Osti, G., & van Strien, D. (2023). Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8375034>

⁹ Including: Digital Repository of Ireland. (2024). End User Agreement. Digital Repository of Ireland. <https://repository.dri.ie/pages/terms>; Digital Repository of Ireland. (2024). Licensing Statement. Digital Repository of Ireland. <https://dri.ie/licensing-statement/>; Digital Repository of Ireland. (2021, December 21). DRI Factsheet No 2: Copyright, Licensing and Open Access. Digital Repository of Ireland. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.v4066146t>; Digital Repository of Ireland. (2020, January 29). DRI Factsheet No. 1: Metadata and the DRI V2. Digital Repository of Ireland. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.bz60sj10d>; Digital Repository of Ireland. (2020, August 26). Qualified Dublin Core and the Digital Repository of Ireland V2. Digital Repository of Ireland. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5425zz83q>

¹⁰ Rights Statements. (2024). <https://rightsstatements.org/>

4. What did it take to get here?

In developing the implementation plan and prioritising the work throughout the project, WP13 started with the discussion notes from meetings of the WorldFAIR Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Working Group and then incorporated feedback from conference and webinar presentations aimed at socialising the five recommendations published in WorldFAIR D13.2. Internal meetings with DRI staff helped to refine the goals, identify technical challenges and plan for the integration of work into DRI's annual work plan. Several DRI staff contributed effort in-kind to the project, including DRI's Senior Software Developer, Junior Software Developer, Senior Software Engineer, Policy Manager, Digital Archivist and Deputy Digital Archivist, to ensure the timely delivery of project outcomes.

Webinars and workshops which fed into the recommendations included: a webinar presentation delivered by DRI for the Research Data Alliance (28 Feb 2023), participation in a Data Exploration workshop hosted by Museum für Kunst und Gewerbe (MK&G) Hamburg (17-21 Apr 2023), a workshop hosted by the 'Collections as Data: Part to Whole' project (25-26 Apr 2023) as well as a workshop on 'Datasheets for Datasets: Describing Web Archives' at the British Library (26 May 2023). In the case of the Collections as Data workshop, the compendium of position statements contributed by participants¹¹ as well as the resulting Vancouver Statement on Collections as Data¹² have been particularly influential in discussions at DRI.

DRI's outreach to socialise and encourage uptake of the recommendations followed with: a poster at the DARIAH annual conference (22 May 2023), a presentation at the LIBER annual conference (6 Jul 2023), a Birds of a Feather session at the SciDataCon International Data Week / Research Data Alliance Plenary (23 Oct 2023), a webinar presentation for DRI's Expert Advisory Group (28 Nov 2023), two webinar presentations as part of the WorldFAIR Outputs and Recommendations series (14 Jun and 6 Dec 2023) and a webinar presentation for a IIF Consortium Community Call (10 Jan 2024). Following the IDW/RDA Plenary event, the project team led the development of an RDA Collections as Data Interest Group to encourage continued collaboration among professionals, projects, infrastructures and services connected via these outreach efforts, to promote exchange between the cultural heritage sector and research data management professionals.

¹¹ Chambers, S., Walsh, M., Caswell, M., Harder, G., Okumura, M., Corrin, J., Baeza Ventura, G., Antonijevic, S., Knazook, B., Narlock, M., Bailey, J., Neudecker, C., Downie, J. S., Layne-Worthey, G., van Strien, D., Irollo, A., Whitmire, A., Lee, J., Berry, D., ... Ridge, M. (2023). Position Statements -> Collections as Data: State of the field and future directions (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7897735>

¹² Padilla, T., Scates Kettler, H., Varner, S., & Shorish, Y. (2023). Vancouver Statement on Collections as Data. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8342171>

The following sections summarise the choices and progress of DRI in implementing and testing the recommendation responses following on from these publication and community consultation efforts, over the course of the last six months of the project. Additional detail and discussion on the topic is available in WorldFAIR D13.3.

4.1. Citation model

Observed in practice: Many cultural heritage institutions do not provide a system-generated citation to researchers on their digital collections platforms, and those that do tend to either use bibliographic standards which do not always map neatly to the metadata available in a cultural heritage record, or they use custom models developed locally. See the example below (Fig 1), also provided in the D13.2 report, from the Digital Public Library of America (DPLA).¹³ The DPLA acts as a content aggregator for American memory collections and was the only image-sharing platform reviewed as part of WP13's mapping of cultural heritage image-sharing platforms which offered auto-generated citations.

¹³ Nourse, Henry King, 1880-1968, ([between 1900 and 1919]) [Cat]. Retrieved from the Digital Public Library of America, https://csl.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma990014663490205115&context=L&vid=01CSL_INST:CSL

Fig 1 - Image of cat on DPLA site, with citation

Options for DRI:

- Continue with existing citation options offered (no change required)
- Choose an existing cultural heritage model to offer as an citation style option
- **Create a new citation style to better represent cultural heritage data**

While DRI already offered several citation styles for end users to choose from to help them properly cite data in the repository (a local style based on CODATA-ICSTI recommendations for research data citation, in addition to MLA, APA, and Chicago citation standards), each of these options reproduced the same issue visible in the DPLA example above: the prioritisation of historical creator names makes it difficult for researchers to easily identify the correct credit holder for the digital records accessed. (In the example above, the metadata record and digital file were provided by the California State Library, which can only be discovered on clicking through to the record itself.)

The point of a citation style is that it acts as both a discovery tool and a credit reference. In combination with other actions being developed in response to the D13.2 recommendation on

[Licensing and Rights](#), it was determined that creating a custom cultural heritage citation style for the repository would assist the end user in the correct application of any licences.

Responding to the need: There were issues encountered along the way as we realised that not all metadata fields were populated consistently by all depositors. As discussed in D13.1, one of the benefits of the Dublin Core Metadata Standard is that it offers users a certain amount of flexibility in how they choose to populate the elements. Concerns were raised about asking members to use Dublin Core in a more limited way simply to produce the expected citation result, and certainly changing DRI’s approach to metadata was felt to be outside the scope of the project.

In the end, the fields selected for testing were those that best provided the kind of information we sought to allow researchers to properly credit and reuse the data, although we acknowledge that there will be instances where the metadata supplied for some objects or collections will not comply with what is expected.

In the citation example taken from DRI’s test environment (Fig 2), the 3D rendering of a 19th century candelabrum produced in Belleek, Co. Fermanagh, Ireland¹⁴ is clearly credited to the Hunt Museum in Limerick as the creator of the file and its associated metadata. The reader can also clearly see that the subject of the data originates in the 19th century, and the data itself is located in the Digital Repository of Ireland at a stable DOI. The specific date and time the material was accessed is given in case the record is updated in the future.

Fig 2 - Image of a cultural heritage object in the repository described using the DRI Cultural Heritage Citation Style

In comparison (Fig 3), the same object cited using the DRI General Citation Style suggests that the 19th century historical creator (or source, in this case) is responsible for a digital object published in

¹⁴ Belleek. (2023, October 16). Belleek Candelabrum, Stags Head. Digital Repository of Ireland; Hunt Museum, Limerick. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.v4066406g>

the repository in 2023. (Readers will note a similar problem with the APA style citation used in the footnotes of this report below.)

Fig 3 - The same cultural heritage object in the repository described using the DRI General Citation Style

Technical work required to implement the changes in the repository utilised [CiteProc-Ruby](#), a citation style repository written in the Ruby programming language, which provides citations in various styles such as APA, Harvard, IEEE, MLA, Vancouver, and Chicago¹⁵. While modifying the CiteProc-Ruby files to implement the custom formats "dri_General" and "dri_Cultural Heritage" would have been an option, we opted to create new independent controllers and methods for these formats to maintain control over future updates. The code for the citation style deployment is available on the DRI GitHub¹⁶.

The citations provided on the CiteProc-Ruby GitHub are well-documented, offering comprehensive guidance. For someone looking to replicate our work in another repository, DRI's technical staff advises thoroughly understanding these standards and leveraging available resources. More discussion of the citation standard development and implementation is available in D13.3.

¹⁵ CiteProc-Ruby (2012). GitHub. <https://github.com/inukshuk/citeproc-ruby>

¹⁶ Digital Repository of Ireland (2024). GitHub. <https://github.com/Digital-Repository-of-Ireland>

From DRI Citation Doc	Implementation Details
{DEPOSITOR}	"Digital Repository of Ireland"
[Depositor]	[Depositor]
{TITLE}	object.title
{CREATOR}	object.creator (Loop all and don't add if == depositing_institute)
{{Creation_Date}}	object.creation_date
{TYPE}	1 st valid type (Primary) or 1 st Type available if no valid type
[Type]	[Type]
{PUBLISHER}	object.publisher or "Digital Repository of Ireland" if empty
{{SysGenDATE}}	object.published_at
	OR object.published_date
[Publisher]	[Publisher]
{DOI URL}	doi
Accessed:	Accessed:
{DATEtimestamp}	Time.current.strftime("YYYY/mm/dd")

	Immutable Strings
	Object variables

Fig 4 - DRI's Cultural Heritage Citation Style Format showing Dublin Core metadata elements and system-generated fields and labels

As of publication, revisions to DRI's existing citation model policy based on the tests conducted are undergoing review by the management team. We anticipate the deployment of the new citation model will take place in early April 2024.

4.2. Transparency

Observed in practice: The GLAM sector has well-established digitisation standards informing common practice in the field, which has produced a remarkable consistency when it comes to scanner resolution, file sizes, bit depth and file formats used by GLAMs. Digitisation workflows, which provide guidance on file management as well as editing images for exhibition, print, or web display, tend to be more varied, with less strict adherence in local adoptions. Guidance on embedding descriptive metadata in files and advice on checking the quality of camera- or device-generated technical metadata, are not necessarily sector-specific but found in resources that cater to a wide variety of industries that utilise and manage digital assets. All this is to say, the data produced by GLAM digitisation practices may look very similar from one institution to another, but the processes used could be wildly different.

As noted in D13.3, 'It is unclear whether many cultural heritage institutions are monitoring the persistence of embedded metadata across versions and formats, or taking proactive steps to embed

additional descriptive metadata into the files to aid interpretation and reuse. It is also unclear to what extent this descriptive metadata, which may be added during the file creation or digitisation process by different persons than those responsible for the creation of descriptive records, may therefore differ from information presented in a metadata record.’

Options:

- **Survey membership about digitisation practices**
- **Develop guidelines for utilising embedded metadata and documenting file creation and management practices**
- Deploy a technical solution to expose embedded image metadata

DRI has, for historical reasons, used a workflow that strips metadata from image files shared with end users to avoid the potential sharing of sensitive information that might be contained therein, such as GPS coordinates, creator contact details and other data points that might reveal names or identifying characteristics that should not be openly shared. Recognising that full transparency is not in itself a requirement of FAIR, which allows for data to be ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary,’ it was determined that the pathway forward on this recommendation required careful consideration to determine the best solution¹⁷. Automatically exposing embedded image metadata raised concerns about privacy (discussed in D13.3) and could potentially introduce conflict with a depositor’s other descriptive metadata.

As noted in D13.3, ‘In considering how DRI could best utilise embedded image file metadata to provide greater visibility of technical information about the format of digital assets, it was agreed that DRI first needed to examine the workflows of members contributing image files to the repository, using that information then to provide feedback on workflows around embedded metadata that could contribute to an overall best practice recommendation. A survey was proposed to capture more information about user workflows to target areas where practices could also improve descriptive as well as technical metadata.’

Responding to the need: A survey of DRI’s members was undertaken to situate institutional practices and the results have been analysed to provide a landscape overview of the technical and descriptive metadata that is currently being captured in files and embedded by members in their workflows. In the coming months DRI will take the findings from this survey and use them to develop practical guidelines for members to support the exposure of technical metadata in line with the FAIR aspiration of being as open as possible, but as closed as necessary. For more information, see ‘Digital Repository of Ireland Member Digitisation Workflows for 2D Image Files: Survey Questions

¹⁷ European Commission Strategy on Research and Innovation (2020-2024). Open Science. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

and Dataset'¹⁸. The results of this survey were also shared at the International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC), 19-21 February 2024, in our presentation 'Creating, retaining and sharing embedded digital image metadata'¹⁹.

Following the analysis of survey results, the solution proposed was to present depositors with a report of the image metadata available in the files ingested into the repository to allow them to reconcile against their collection and object records, and utilise the information as needed. This work has yet to be approved through the relevant DRI task forces before it can be added to the development workflow.

4.3. Datasheets

Observed in practice: Context documentation is very important to the cultural heritage sector, but it was noted in D13.1 that there is often an absence of contextual information pertaining to the acquisition and digitisation processes that inform the creation and scope of digital collections. Critically, this information is necessary to mitigate the potential harms in using cultural heritage data in big data research inquiries²⁰.

Addressing this issue is an emerging range of data collection description formats described as datasheets, data cover sheets, data packages, data cards, etc. These resources encourage transparency around collection management actions such as: defining the scope of the collection (in terms of subject coverage but also, for example, in relation to the non-digital holdings of an institution), describing how the data was processed, and providing important provenance information relating to the management and reuse of digital files over the lifetime of the objects.

Options:

- **Enhance DRI's existing guidance on providing contextual information**
- Develop a datasheet template to depositors based on a review of community examples
- **Use an existing datasheet template developed for purpose**

Rather than having to create a bespoke datasheet, the project team is in the fortunate position of being able to build on the work of others. Developments in the cultural heritage sector supporting the use of datasheets include:

¹⁸ Knazook, B., Cassidy, K., O'Brien, M. and Murphy, J. (2024). 'Digital Repository of Ireland Member Digitisation Workflows for 2D Image Files: Survey Questions and Dataset'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10849045> (Accessed: 21 March 2024).

¹⁹ <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc24/programme>

²⁰ Ames, S., & Lewis, S. (2020). Disrupting the library: Digital scholarship and Big Data at the National Library of Scotland. *Big Data & Society*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951720970576>

- ❖ [Digitized Books Data Cover Sheet](#) by LC Labs
- ❖ [Hugging Face Contentious Contexts Datasheet](#) by the Cultural AI lab NL
- ❖ [De Boer Press Photography Data Sheet](#) by Melvin Wevers *et al*
- ❖ [Unsilencing Colonial Archives via Automated Entity Recognition Data Card](#) by Mrinalini Luthra *et al*.
- ❖ [DNBL OCR Data Set Description](#) by KB Lab
- ❖ [Digitised Books Dataset Documentation](#) by the British Library.

Given these excellent resources to utilise, which were each developed to fit the needs of specific projects and outputs, DRI has opted to test the standardised template published in July 2023 as ‘Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets’ in the Journal of Open Humanities Data. This datasheet was developed by a [Europeana Working Group](#), launched in September 2022 as a collaborative project between the Europeana Research Community and EuropeanaTech Community, in recognition that more transparency around the acquisition, management, processing and delivery of cultural heritage data is required to support the responsible reuse by researchers across disciplines. The authors acknowledge that digital cultural heritage datasets ‘are often the product of multiple layers of selection; they may have been created for different purposes than establishing a statistical sample according to a specific research question; they change over time and are heterogeneous.’²¹ The template was presented as a draft for community testing and review, and shortly after publication a call went out for participants to test and refine the template. The purpose and design of this template directly responds to the guidance provided by the WorldFAIR Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Working Group to encourage depositors to surface technical and administrative metadata to better contextualise collections.²² As a national aggregator for Europeana, DRI is further encouraged to support the testing of this datasheet to provide feedback in the development of best practice in the area.

Responding to the need: DRI already supports the addition of contextual documentation for collections or sub-collections in the form of related or supporting digital files, and provides guidance on how to contribute enhanced contextual information. DRI’s own research projects demonstrate good practice in providing related contextual information, for example, records supporting the dataset [‘Repeal the Eighth and Reproductive Rights: Organisers Interviews.’](#)

Depositors will find the ‘Add Documentation’ button under the ‘Editor Tools’ section on the collection page (Fig 5). When ‘Add Documentation’ is selected this prompts the depositor to create

²¹ Alkemade, H., Claeysens, S., Colavizza, G., Freire, N., Lehmann, J., Neudecker, C., Osti, G., & van Strien, D. (2023). Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets. Journal of Open Humanities Data, 9(17). <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.124>

²² WorldFAIR Project (D13.2) Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report.

a new object within that collection. The depositor then uses the familiar Add Object UI webform to add metadata associated with the supporting document. Note that the process of selecting ‘Add Documentation’ creates the ‘has Documentation’ and the ‘Is Documentation For’ relationship between the collection and the object. If the depositor was to select ‘Add an Object’, this relationship would not be established.²³

Fig 5 - Screenshot of Editor Tools sidebar on the Collections page

At the moment, DRI is developing training and guidance to encourage members to utilise these datasheets, recognising that there may be significant challenges for GLAM professionals in collecting a lot of the information requested (as evidenced by the survey results documented in work on [Transparency](#)). The datasheet authors suggest an approach to management which does not enforce a minimum compliance, which would see datasheets as records which may evolve over time and in response to reuse of collections. DRI will attempt to incorporate this understanding into our approach to encouraging the adoption of datasheets for member collections.

4.4. Licensing and rights

Observed in practice: Cultural heritage organisations are usually very good at identifying and communicating rights information to end users, though the practice is far from standardised across the sector and the communication of rights information may sometimes be combined with implied licences as well. Creative Commons licences, which are widely used by research data repositories to

²³ <https://repository.dri.ie/catalog/sn00qc64j>

indicate reuse permissions, are also adopted by a number of image-sharing platforms that serve the cultural heritage sector.²⁴

As stewards of memory collections, DRI members usually either hold the rights to materials in their collections or they are able to act on behalf of the rights holder to licence materials. DRI has been able to leverage this to enforce a requirement for a separate licence field to be populated before data can be published in the repository. Members have also been advised via DRI publications that metadata is provided under a CC0 or CC-BY licence.

Options:

- **Add Rights Statements to encourage standardised rights language**
- **Add a metadata statement to the record page to make clear that the data and metadata may be licenced separately**
- Licence information is already required and users are advised via DRI publications that metadata is CC0 or CC-BY, leave rights field alone (no change)

Responding to the need: Although the CC0 licence requirement for metadata is clearly communicated to any depositors who wish to have their content aggregated to Europeana, DRI did not previously provide a mechanism for this information to be displayed to end users. There was also no way for depositors to indicate to end users when they preferred CC-BY, which may have been the case in certain circumstances. Providing this information required a fairly simple technical solution to provide a statement on the landing page of all records. An example of how this will look is shown below (Fig 6).

²⁴ WorldFAIR Project (D13.1) Cultural Heritage Mapping Report: Practices and policies supporting Cultural Heritage image sharing platforms.

Fig. 6 - Screenshot of the end of a metadata record in DRI's test environment showing the default CC0 metadata statement

The provision of standardised rights and licence fields required the creation of a new fixed-value field called 'Copyright Status' which displays as a drop-down menu to depositors. The options populated in this field are taken from [RightsStatements.org](https://rightsstatements.org), which have already had some uptake in the cultural heritage sector (Fig 7). Modifications to the existing Licence field include a label change to 'Re-use Licence' and a stream-lining of options in the drop-down menu (Fig 8).

Fig 7 - Copyright Status drop-down menu in DRI test environment

Fig 8 - Licence field options reduced and renamed 'Re-use Licence' in DRI test environment

As discussed in D13.3, the technical solutions for this implementation were the easy part. It is anticipated that outreach to DRI members to ensure appropriate deployment of metadata licences to past records will continue past the end of the WorldFAIR project.

4.5. Delivery

Observed in practice: In D13.1 it was acknowledged that image-sharing is a particular strength of the cultural heritage sector, compared to other research domains. As noted in D13.1 section 2.1 (Enabling Practices), cultural heritage image-sharing platforms ‘...utilise the metadata standards developed by the communities they serve and they support exchange using community-approved technologies and systems, typically selected from open source and non proprietary solutions.’ The few improvements to delivery technologies suggested in D13.2, under the recommendation for ‘Delivery’, identified technologies that DRI already supported: DRI offers an API to query collections, utilises the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) to provide detailed images and their metadata, metadata records support Linked Open Data, and both collections and objects receive persistent identifiers (PIDS) upon publication. Of course there is always room for improvement, but it was unclear where to target the effort for the time available in the WorldFAIR project.

Options:

- **Develop use cases to support further technical developments**
- Implement a SPARQL endpoint in the repository

- Review Linked Open Data (LOD) support

Technical enhancements to DRI should come from user-driven needs assessment, which suggests that the best way forward is to encourage users to play with the current repository functionality and to give feedback in a structured way. Rather than pursue a particular technical solution out of interest or anticipated need, DRI decided to develop collection reuse cases to lead future development.

Responding to the need: DRI has developed a workshop outline and a sample use case for students at the University of Limerick to explore and reuse repository collections, a project developed in collaboration with DPASSH conference co-hosts and organisers at the Glucksman Library, University of Limerick, for June 2024. It is hoped that this type of structured event can provide a model for further training and reuse of cultural heritage data in DRI's collections. The sample use case is available as an appendix to D13.3.

5. Conclusion

DRI has mapped out an ambitious plan to respond to each of the recommendations published in WorldFAIR D13.2. The technical work required to support two recommendations has been completed in the test environment, supported by considerable discussion of the implications for practice and policy, also outlined in some detail in D13.3. Ongoing work to ensure continued progress towards the goals described here forms a key part of DRI's upcoming schedule of training, outreach and engagement in 2024.